

EFFECTIVE WAYS OF USING NON-VERBAL COMMUNICATION IN REDUCING TEACHER TALKING TIME

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Abstract. *This article explores the significance of reducing teacher talking time (TTT) in the classroom and examines diverse strategies to accomplish the goal. In today's modern teaching, high levels of TTT have been consistently associated with decreased student engagement, limited chances for active learning, and diminished student engagement. In the light of implementing effective and efficient techniques and increasing a student involvement during the classes, educators ideally can create a more learner-centered learning environment, which positively effect on improving students' motivation, well-gained comprehension and overall achievement. This article highlights evidence-based strategies, such as utilizing body language, visual aids and using silence and pauses during the classes. The findings suggest that applying for below-mentioned techniques during the classes gives a great chance to educators to have more innovative, communicative and learner-centered classes.*

Keywords: *reducing TTT, learner-centered classes, maximize STT, communicative, collaborative, techniques, gestures, eye-contact.*

“The greatest enemy to students learning is the talking teacher”

John Holt (American educator)

INTRODUCTION. It is not a secret that traditional teaching approaches heavily rely on the educators' role where the teacher serves as the primary source of information and this approach often involves a passive role of the learner because in these methods, the teachers are dominant during the classes and deliver the information solely. However, today's modern teaching approaches require educators to have more dynamic and student-centered classes. To tackle this issue, reducing Teacher Talking Time (TTT) by means of utilizing non-verbal communication is a brand new innovative and effective approach that has gained empirical attention in educational areas. This research investigates the potential effectiveness of decreasing the amount of time teachers spend during classes and explores several alternative means of communication which help the teachers to foster student engagement and participation. By harnessing the effectiveness of non-verbal communication, such as body language, visual support, silence and pauses, educators have a great chance to create a more interactive and dynamic learning environment. The main aim of the study is to examine those strategies and techniques that can be utilized to minimize Teacher Talking Time while still promoting more student-engaged classes. The need for reducing teacher talking time, the effectiveness of using body language, visual supports, silence and pauses to decrease TTT will be tackled in the case study through the analysis of existing articles, empirical studies and the writer's personal view.

The Need for Reducing Teacher Talking Time

Today's modern English teachers are always curious about how to make their classes more dynamic and student-engaged. To deal with this issue, there is a need to minimize teachers' talking time and maximize the learners' engagement. There are several reasons why should the teacher's talking time be minimized and one of them is that it leads the learners to loss of concentration, boredom and reducing learning. Moreover, when the teacher speaks too much, the learners do not have a chance to engage. Then, it leads to have a decreased interaction and communication between the teacher and learners during the class, which eventually causes to have less effective teaching process. Furthermore, there are potential benefits from decreasing teacher talking time, and one of them is that the more students speak the more the teacher has a chance to give feedback and focuses on the learner's needs. Eventually, it leads students to work on their mistakes and develop their knowledge. Besides this, the learner can enhance communicative and speaking skills. Therefore, the purpose of my study is to explore the effectiveness of several techniques of using non-verbal communication during the classes.

The Significance of Using Body Language

Many educators highlight that one of the most empirical approaches to reducing teacher talking time is using body language during classes. This technique helps teachers to demonstrate their thoughts and instructions in a much clearer and visible way. It has been identified that the purpose of non-verbal communication was answered as a tool of supporting communication by 46% of teachers (Kasikci, 2023). This percentage can be much higher if the teachers, who conduct the classes in a traditional way, feel the effectiveness of utilizing body language. Proper body language in a classroom setting gives you the ability to motivate, inspire and engage. Besides this, using body language not only reduces teacher talking time, but also gives the teachers the confidence about what they are teaching and the learners also feel enough confidence to speak and participate in the lessons more frequently. Moreover, Sillars (1995) identifies that there are seven types of body language: face expressions, head movements, hand-arm movements, position and body posture, standing and sitting, legs and feet including eyes and body contact. A Turkish researcher, Kasikci, also posts in his research report that 82% of teachers use eye contact to warn students. It suggests that it is better to keep eye contact to warn the learner than make them feel discriminated against or offended by saying something in front of other classmates.

Classification of body language according to Sillars

The chart describes the classification of body language which was classified by Sillars.

Body language conveys warmth and empathy and it reminds the learners that the teacher is approachable and there to help. Diverse types of body language play various roles up to circumstances. Let's take the teachers keeping open arms as an example. An open-armed body position signals an invitation to the learners. It refers to welcoming new ideas and brainstorming. In light of this tactic, the learners feel free to speak and take part in the activities. Moreover, this posture is also a great way to draw the students' attention to the teacher and, therefore, learners will be more likely to listen to what the teacher has to say. In my teaching life, I personally use several types of body language, such as facial expressions and safe touch to for the learners. Safe touch helps me to strengthen my words' effects and establish good communication with my learners. By analyzing the types of body language, it can be comprehended that expressive facial cues, hand gestures can help the learners to speak more and elaborate on their ideas.

Furthermore, body language is considered not only as a tool of communication, but also comprehension via physical movements and changes that show a person's thoughts and attitudes. The more the instructors use body dialect prompts effectively and fittingly, the more learners' comprehension is ideally to be improved. Wallac (1982) posts that "How to educate is more critical than what to educate." Moreover, Phipps (2012: 7-10) presents the main functions and uses of body language as follows: 1) In some circumstances where verbal communication (words) do not work delivers such situations body language poses a role as an instruction or code and deliver the information to the learners; 2) Body language makes a difference to demonstrate the word being utilized, here body dialect plays as a pointer. For example, if the student says 'YES', but shakes his or her head from side to side indicating 'NO', others are more likely listen to the meaning 'NO'. 3) Body language can to work as an emphasize. It is clear from the findings that, in some cases, the body language is mostly used as a tool of the learners' comprehension.

The Effectiveness of Using Visual Aids

Another significant technique in decreasing TTT in classes is using visual aids. Visual support such as pictures, posters, charts, web pages or technological devices add more clarity to the teacher's talk and predictability for what might come next (Asher, TPR, 1966). Clansy nad Hruska (2005) claim that students can also demonstrate comprehension of verbal commands through visible expressions or by active involvement with language skills. As we know, there are four types of student learning style, including visual learning, in which the majority of students learn through pictures or video presentations better. This is because visual support has more appeal while compared to the written texts, especially for young learners. It is very curious. Many studies have been conducted on the power and the effectiveness of using visual aids so that the teachers speak less, such as learning through visuals helps students to study more effectively. By means of visuals, learners can easily visualize what is being delivered by the teacher, and learning through visuals helps the learners to retain the information for a long time. It means that they can easily remember what has been taught with the help of visualization during the class. Besides these, it helps them to gain fittingly a proper view of topics and concepts. One more empirical benefit of using visual support during classes is that it makes the process of teaching easier for educators. More specifically, sometimes it becomes difficult for the teachers to deliver the information which is in the educator's mind without visuals. Finally, visual aids create an atmosphere of interest in the class. Diverse pictures and colorful posters ideally help educators to create an atmosphere of interest during the classes. Personally, I very often use visual aids during my classes, especially short videos related to my topic. It gives me some time to think about further steps in the teaching

process and, besides this, the learners can refresh their minds and can have a chance to visualize what is being taught during the lesson.

The Power of Pauses and Silence

Last but not least effective way of reducing teacher talking time is using pauses and silence during the classes. Experimental studies in pausology have shown that “the length and frequency of pauses are correlated with the process of the speaker’s lexical and semantic choices” (Bazzanella, 1994). It indicates that a proper use of pauses and silence plays a great role in teaching process to hold lexical and semantic choices. Moreover, Orletti (2000) outlines that “the participants do not accomplish of communicative rights or obligations, but differentiate for unequal access to the power of managing the interaction”. It means that by means of utilizing silence and pauses, there will appear a balance between the teacher and learners where they take turns to speak and interact with each other. Eventually, it is a great choice for the educators to increase the learners’ talking time. Moreover, according to Zhang (2008), the quality of learning process is totally linked with the quality of classroom interaction and discourse, and this is the reason why a teacher should encourage his or her learners to generate their questions and answers and make them get involved more and more in authentic tasks, such as speaking activities. Therefore, it is important for the teachers keep in mind the role of teacher talking and student talking so they can fully utilize TT and ST.

As an addition to the above mentioned quotas on the power of using silence and pauses in English classes to minimize the amount of time teachers use, there is also a claim on the issue that the thematic organization can ideally be controlled but the educators and the classroom represents an asymmetrical interaction when teachers do not attribute speaking turn (Candella, 1999; Go’mez A.; Mauri M., 2000). It should be admitted that the teacher is considered a stakeholder who totally controls the thematic organization of the class according to lesson plan. Then, the teachers themselves are responsible for leading a symmetrical interaction and devote much of time to the learners to get engaged and take their turns. It is true that in most cases we, educators, underestimate the power of our silence presence to help us form a deep connection with our learners. In my teaching process, if I want to receive the students’ responses I do not ask direct question, but look at the learners, smile and keep the silence. Then, in most situations the students understand that they are expected to respond and have a turn to speak

CONCLUSION. How to make the classes more dynamic and student-engaged is always a crucial issue among English language teachers. Reducing teacher's talking time by means of non-verbal communication is a highly potential technique to achieve the goal. From the collected data and existing articles, it is clear that the use of body language, such as gestures, facial expressions; utilizing visual aids to deliver the information and while giving the instructions; the use of silence and pauses by the educators pose a great role in minimizing the amount of time the teachers spend during the classes. The techniques provided in the case study are not only helpful to increase the learners’ talking time, but also they ideally help them to comprehend easily, to increase the interest and to remember the information for a long time. In my opinion, it is sometimes more impressive to show your expressions or just keeping silence than just producing the words. An American educator, John Holt (1959), states that “The enemy of the student learning is the talking teacher”. The quote would probably be a great concluding statement for the issue in the research. That means that a talking teacher plays the role of a distracter who does not let his or her learner speak and interact during the class. The less teachers speak, the more learners have a chance to take the

dominance and they start to take self-learning responsibilities. I do believe that those above-mentioned techniques are ideally helpful and need further deep studies to implement them into practice.

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